

***Purpuricenus wachanrui schoenfeldti* Heyden, 1890 (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) from Iran is a valid name**

M.A. Lazarev¹, R. Ambrus²

¹Free Economic Society of Russia, Department of Scientifics Conferences and All-Russian Projects

Bolshaya Tatarskaya str., 35, build. 3, Moscow 115184 Russia

e-mail: cerambycidae@bk.ru; humanityspace@gmail.com

ORCID 0000-0002-4040-0987

²Trnkovo nám. 1112/1, CZ-152 00 Praha 5, Czech Republic

e-mail: ambrus@centrum.cz

Key words: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, taxonomy, new synonym, Iran.

Abstract. *Purpuricenus wachanrui schoenfeldti* Heyden, 1890, **nom. rest.** = *Purpuricenus robusticollis* Pic, 1905, **syn. n.**

The taxon was originally described as a variation *Purpuricenus wachanrui* var. *schoenfeldti* Heyden, 1890. Later it was generally (Aurivillius, 1912; Winkler, 1929; Plavilstshikov, 1940, Özdikmen, 2025) accepted as an aberration of *P. wachanrui* Levrat, 1858. Recently the name was often published (Löbl & Smetana, 2010; Miroshnikov, 2012; Danilevsky, 2020; Özdikmen, 2021) as a synonym of *P. wachanrui*.

Purpuricenus robusticollis Pic, 1905 was originally described as a species and was so accepted (Aurivillius, 1912; Winkler, 1929; Löbl & Smetana, 2010; Ambrus & Grosser, 2013; Danilevsky, 2020).

Danilevsky & Hodek (2024) downgraded the name to subspecies rank *P. wachanrui robusticollis* Pic, 1905.

Now we received a photo of the holotype (female) of *P. wachanrui* var. *schoenfeldti* Heyden, 1890 (Figs 1-2) designated as lectotype by G. Sama, but never published. It is preserved in Senckenberg Deutsches Entomologisches Institut, Müncheberg. It is really totally black and about 15 mm long.

Photo of the holotype (male) of *Purpuricenus robusticollis* Pic, 1905 (Figs 3-5) from National Museum of Natural History, Paris

M.A. Lazarev, R. Ambrus

is also available. The both specimens are clearly conspecific. A remarkable character of the holotype of *P. wachanrui* var. *schoenfeldti* Heyden - small red spot on the curved elytral margin, mentioned in its original description is clearly seen in the holotype of *Purpuricenus robusticollis* Pic.

So, *Purpuricenus wachanrui schoenfeldti* Heyden, 1890, **nom. rest.** = *Purpuricenus robusticollis* Pic, 1905, **syn. n.**

The study of big series of the taxon from different localities (Danilevsky & Hodek, 2024) shows a great degree of its variability. Pronotum sometimes can be partly or totally red and elytra can have wide red transverse band or a pair of red spots.

Acknowledgements. We are very grateful to Ms. Momo Larisch (Senckenberg Deutsches Entomologisches Institut, Müncheberg) and Dr. Gérard Tavakilian (National Museum of Natural History, Paris) for supplying us with holotype photos.

REFERENCES

- Ambrus R. & Grosser W. 2013. Results of the Czech entomological expedition to Iran (2009-2010) (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae). - Humanity space. International almanac. 2 (3): 461-482.
- Aurivillius C. 1912. Cerambycidae: Cerambycinae. Pars 39. - In: Schenkling S. (ed.): Coleopterorum Catalogus. Volumen 22. Cerambycidae I. Berlin: Junk, 108 + 574 pp.
- Danilevsky M.L. & Hodek K. 2024. A complex of taxa around *Purpuricenus wachanrui* Levrat, 1858 (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae). - Humanity space. International almanac. 13 (8): 662-687. DOI: 10.24412/2226-0773-2024-13-8-662-687.
- Heyden L.F.J.D. von 1890. *Purpuricenus wachanrui* Levrat und seine Varietäten. Deutsche Entomologische Zeitschrift 1890: 79.
- Löbl I. & Smetana A. (ed.) 2010. Catalogue of Palearctic Coleoptera, vol. 6. Chrysomeloidea. Stenstrup, Apollo Books: 924 pp.
- Miroshnikov A. I. 2012. Contribution to the knowledge of the longicorn beetles of the Caucasus. 8. Genus *Purpuricenus* Dejean, 1821 (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae). Caucasian entomological bulletin. 8 (1): 37-50.
- Özdikmen, H. 2025. A taxonomic evaluation on the genus *Purpuricenus* Dejean with proposition of a new subgenus (Cerambycidae: Cerambycinae). Munis Entomology & Zoology. 20 (2): 2777-2798.
- Özdikmen, H. 2021. An annotated catalogue: Cerambycoidea (Cerambycidae and Vesperidae) of Turkey (Coleoptera). Munis Entomology & Zoology. 16 (Supplement): 1273-1556.

M.A. Lazarev, R. Ambrus

- Pic M. 1905. Descriptions et Notes Diverses. - Matériaux pour servir à l'étude des Longicornes. 5 (2): 5-15.
- Pic M. 1956. Coléoptères du globe (suite). - L'Échange, Revue Linnéenne. 72 (543): 1-4.
- Plavilstshikov N.N. 1940. Fauna SSSR. Nasekomye zhestokrylye. T. XXII. Zhuki-drovoseki (ch. 2). Moskva - Leningrad: Izdatel'stvo Akademii Nauk SSSR, 784 + [3] pp. [in Russian]
- Winkler A. 1929. Cerambycidae. - In: Catalogus Coleopterorum regionis palaearcticae. Winkler et Wagner, Wien, pp. 1135-1226.

Figs 1-2. *Purpuricenus wachanrui schoenfeldti* Heyden, 1890, **nom. rest.** (Photos by Momo Larisch): 1. Holotype, female; 2. Labels of the holotype.

Figs 3-5. *Purpuricenus robusticollis* Pic, 1905 (Photos by Dr. Gérard Tavakilian): 3. Holotype, male, dorsal view; 4. Holotype, male, lateral view; 5. Labels of the holotypes.

Received: 21.11.2025
Accepted: 12.12.2025